
Strategies For Student Participation with Remote Online Learning: Instructor Expectations

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Abstract

This report would explore potential methods to improve student participation with remote online learning. The research showed that online learners make use of a variety of technical applications. Survey of LA1's confirms that technical applications like Zoom, Padlets, Nearpod, Flipgrid, Mentimeter, Boom Cards, and Vocaroo were the most widely utilized technological technology. It confirms that pads and cards play a valuable function in inspiring students to learn successfully in online learning climate. According to the finding of this report, student participation is a tactic without the use of technologies.

1. Introduction

The onset of COVID 19 triggered massive disturbances at our colleges, causing a lot of student chaos. It is projected that there are about 1.700 billion students impacted by the epidemic (Daily Sabbah, 2020). More than 130 countries have imposed a mandatory closure of schools to deal with the upcoming pandemic. (CNA, 2020). This closing of the LSBC also made many LSBC trainees emphasize studying and teaching in the machine. This abrupt transition from conventional classroom education to online education has created issues and demands explanation. According to this report, online learning had difficulties in internet access, internet affordability for students, equality of learning, opportunities for online learning, the anxiety induced during online learning, and interaction of the students online. Data indicates that elevated levels of anxiety impair the academic success of children (Ironsi, 2017). This research is scarce and restricted. This present paper would help educational officials ensure that education is delivered even in such complicated circumstances. There would be some improvements in student learning because of the interactive world or processes (Paulsen & McCormick, 2020). This could significantly influence the learning

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attitudes of students. This research seeks to explore methods for improving the interaction of online students.

To define the educational condition in Northern Cyprus by the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus Minister of Education. The educational structure of NC covers pre-school, basic, secondary, and university schooling (Hale & Ali, 2019). This tiny island's educational ideologies focused on universalism and freedom (Shola, Selira & Mustafa, 2011). The higher education industry has contributed to the economic growth by drawing many international students into the region (Hale et al., 2019). It is admonished that the GDP of North Carolina, USA in 2007 was \$14.768 billion and that the educational sector contributed almost half. Most colleges have followed a holistic approach to education and have made space for an ecosystem in which international students can encounter each other and learn about their varied cultures. This thesis means that the spread of the COVID 19 pandemic has placed a stop to academic activity and jeopardized the hopes of millions of international students wishing to study in other nations. So, there is a need to involve the students who are not doing well in a remote online learning center.

The pandemic has had negative impacts on global schooling. If these international students choose the remote online education, they would experience the lack of interest in this mode of education. A proper instructor orientation for student involvement is important for student achievement during today's tumultuous times. Online schooling in the Northern Cyprus has been available since 2006. (Shola et al, 2011). Other reports also say that flipped classroom formats have been helpful for teaching and learning in north Cyprus . (Tugun, Uzunboylu, & Ozdamli, 2017). It is assumed that flipped learning has enhanced more social and immersive learning throughout the learning process (Odo & Eze, 2017). We would evaluate the effectiveness or failure of the Xray teaching methodologies utilized in this pandemic because of the lack of trials to date, this will help us determine its strengths and disadvantages.

After the virus epidemic, the government issued an ultimatum for all schools to teach and learn online (Yakin Dogu Universitesi, 2020). This abrupt shift of universities into online learning encouraged students to pursue interest in online courses (The University of Kyrenia, 2020). Both teachers and admin have little time to make changes for evolving training practices. This condition promotes the involvement of teachers and students with learning that may arise. The teachers were able to provide quality training sessions with the usage of quality teaching materials, and their superior teaching skills. One of the difficulties of Internet Learning and teaching is the need to inspire and stimulate people to engage during classes (Sridharan & Bond, 2019). This study finds that North Cyprus's situation isn't different and there is a need to inspire international students to enroll in higher education. In this case it was important to use proficient methods such as 'reciprocal evaluation' (Karafil & Oguz, 2019). Such resources can include; (1) Successfully sharing knowledge for various levels of learning styles; (2) Peer group debate splits out the learners into separate classes. This research believes that utilizing techniques to promote learning participation during this influenza pandemic would improve students' engagement in a remote online teaching scenario.

2. Materials and Methods

The analytical structure

The interaction of teachers with students will help reduce the spread of flu. Student involvement is crucial for any learners because it lets students remain involved and centered in the language learning phase. This philosophy encourages community work through learning as it

maintains students centered and committed (Mavromoustakos, 2017). According to this principle, technology allows student participation more successful and productive (Maia, Figueiredo, & Serey, 2019; Sridharan & Bond, 2019). This purpose of engagement philosophy seeks to foster student engagement when in the classroom. The research aligns with the idea that participation is the primary component in stimulating students interest. Studies have often illustrated that it is impossible for students to remember knowledge because they are not inspired to study them. In periods where students are exposed to extreme stress and anxiety as the consequence of the emergence of a pandemic, and a new learning method, it's crucial to have opportunities for resilience between students (Groves, Sellars, Smith & Barber, 2015). This study says that students ought to be involved not only by utilizing devices but also by meeting face to face. This research would explore different modes of involving students either electronically or otherwise during the COVID 19 pandemic epidemic.

A key aspect in online learning is the student's interest. You would have to adopt those principles for participating L2 Learning in remote online (Stone, 2019). Certain values should be followed when attempting to implement participation. Learning through partnership is one of them. Practices should promote cooperation. This will unveil certain cognitive skills (Ekblaw, 2016). Groups of learners function together in a community environment as they share information to complete a mission collaboratively (Demosthenous et al., 2020). This is accomplished by project-based activities which compel learner to carry out the project work individually (Ekblaw, 2016; Ragusa & Crampton, 2018). Thanks to the students' active and imaginative efforts during the project implementation (Ekblaw, 2016). They master these skills by doing them in the class. The teachers play a vital role in creating fun and interesting classroom experiences that will inspire students to engage during classes (Redzuan, Lokman, Ali-Othman & Abdullah, 2016). It is agreed that the teacher needs to plan engaging task, classroom experiences that are worthwhile and authentic task to meaningfully involve students throughout an online session, which will assist keep the students focused and inspired during the learning time. studies conclude that continuity in carrying out these engagements allows the online learning a worthwhile encounter (Sridharan & Bond, 2019). This research affirms that these techniques will keep students encouraged to utilize the web-based remote learning resources throughout the pandemic epidemic.

Online learning is seen as enhancing excitement and participation during class teaching (Ritchhart, Church & Morrison, 2011). Others claim the engagement should be made despite utilizing technologies or not (Philp & Duchesne, 2016; Demosthenous et al., 2020). Teachers should carefully choose the learning resources to use in directing students' attention. The usage of technical technologies and networks has become commonplace; teachers can use the ability of technology to educate (Paulsen & McCormick, 2020). Often, technical oriented systems are being utilized in a way where the learners can train their brains and understand meaning by their teaching. Mentimeter is a participatory assessment method that students will use anonymously to question and validate classmates' thought (Beth, 2020). They will help students be interested in online learning.

One of the key things that online learning is focused on is community engagement and the use of technical resources including padlets, flipgrid, vocaroo, and zoom breakout rooms is successful (Kleinsmith, 2017). They are methods used to promote independent thought and questioning (Ekblaw, 2016). Learners should use padlets as an online space to express their insights and opinions about a given subject that normally stimulates several debates. Students should be allowed to give their views with the assistance of springboards which the instructor reads and addresses (Kleinsmith, 2017). Learners are involved because their ideas are addressed in this Socratic discourse (Fuchs, 2014). Like a padlet, flipgrid allows community conversation with the potential to submit photographs and remarks to the exchange. There are a number of technical and learning tools that teachers and learners can use to make remote learning fun and inspiring. It is vital for

teachers to teach young students to employ clever methods in order to attain their career goals. It's often necessary to inspire them and assist them to appreciate their classes.

In the latest research.

Some researchers have mentioned that students have to play an active role in improving learning experience (Paulsen & McCormick, 2020; Mai et al., 2019; Karfil et al, 2019,). This paper looks at what should be achieved in the curriculum to better fit the new learner now. This paper claims that various resources are accessible to teachers to select and utilize with their online courses. This thesis aimed to explore instructional techniques either in terms of money, expertise, or technical tools for remote online learning during influenza pandemic outbreak. We performed an analysis to address these concerns.

- Which methods and services were used in remote online learning?
- Will these practices be seen in remote online learning?
- What is the view of the learners on the usage of tools or technologies for online learning?

The study followed a cross-sectional qualitative mixed-method approach. This approach includes both qualitative and quantitative methods to gather knowledge from consumers (Yildirim & Simsek, 2011). This study design would be able to elicit insightful knowledge regarding educational methods, techniques, and services utilized by undergraduate students during this Pandemic epidemic. This research will gather data via questionnaires and interview answers. English units were also used for instruction before the coronavirus epidemic and were used for the analysis of the course. The course was taught online at the time of coronavirus epidemic. Educational educational tools are deployed throughout every simulated classroom to inspire students and arouse their curiosity in learning, this lasted for eight weeks and two days. Questionnaires and interviews were used to elicit details for this analysis.

Participants.

Participants in this sample consisted of 63 ELT preservice teachers from a private university in north Cyprus. They selected students remotely utilizing a purposive sampling technique. For the interviews, 12 individuals were chosen randomly. Students gave their permission and were able to engage in the study experiment. For interviews.

The data collection

A questionnaire was employed to capture the data and semi-structured questions were used to obtain the details. Both portions are comprised of 12 response things and eight items. The questionnaire was structured to fulfill our analysis goals. The section A of the questionnaire was structured on a 5 point Likert style scale of Often (5) sometimes (4) often (3) Sometimes (2) and Never (1) and was used to assess the efficacy of utilizing online teaching services through 8 separate scales of effectiveness. Thus, five speech questions were used to address the third research question on learners' perspective on the usage of engagement tools and technology during online learning. These questionnaires were also repeated to make sure that they assess what they are expected to measure. A usability review of the questionnaire found that the test was fair useful in evaluating what it aims to assess (2003). Interviews were registered, transcribed and downloaded from zoom.

3. Results and Discussions

It was evaluated to evaluate the mean answers on gathered resources, methods, and approaches used in online education. Interviews were transcribed and the recommendations from the participants were exploited for instructional purposes.

Results of the experiment:

The survey findings presented below.

Part A.

RQ1: What resources, skills, and tools were used during remote online learning?

Table 1: Mean responses of learners on resources, skills, and tools used during remote online learning

Scale	N	Mean	SD
Zoom application was used during lessons	63	4.00	0.19
The teacher uses Zoom break out room for group work/ projects	63	4.55	0.61
We used Nearpod application for self-graded assessment	63	4.02	0.69
Games were used during lessons	63	4.85	0.95
Padlet was used to share the opinions of students during lessons	63	4.27	0.12
The teachers made an audio recording with vocaroo and the students responded to the discussion by making their recording	63	2.35	1.88
Mentimeter was used to seek our opinions on a topic	63	4.18	0.68
We discussed topics in groups using flipgrid	63	4.79	0.78
Boom cards were used in between lessons to ensure students are learning	63	4.88	0.87
The teacher introduces projects/tasks to be accomplished	63	4.69	0.34
Peer teaching was effective during online learning	63	2.56	1.24
The teacher allowed more interaction by the students during lessons	63	4.34	0.57

Table 1 presents the means for resources, expertise, and tools utilized by the participants on the remote online learning. These findings show that a mean score of 4.00 (0.19) and 4.55 (0.61) was achieved when participants were questioned whether online remote lessons and breaks out rooms were included. The participants remembered that their instructor used the zoom application

and breakout rooms to help them in their community work. The table shows that a mean of 4.02 (0.69) was registered when asked participants were asked whether Nearpod application had been used in self-graded tests. In comparison, sports, utilizing padlets program, Mentimeter, flipgrid, boom cards, were the most widely used technologies during lessons and remote online courses. This research found that the use of vocaroo for teaching students online was hardly utilized.

This suggests that instructor also used assignment and job methods while conducting online classes, the mean value was 0.34 (above 50%) which suggested so. When it comes to peer teaching as one of the resources to support online learners, the findings suggest that peer teaching is just not helpful at all. This suggested that there was a mean value of 4.34 (0.57) as participants indicated to the degree to which their teachers enabled them to participate in contact with their peers. This result indicated that the primary instructor provided for frequent contact during class.

Part B.

RQ2: How adequate were these resources when used during remote online learning?

*Table 2:
Mean responses of learners on the effectiveness of resources used during remote online learning*

	N	M	SD
Effectiveness index scale			
The use of teaching resources achieved lesson objectives	63	4.77	0.78
The use of teaching resources made classroom activities more organized	63	4.65	0.69
The use of teaching resources enhanced collaborative learning	63	4.02	0.41
Videos were clear during lessons	63	2.24	1.02
The resources had a high audio quality	63	2.67	1.46
It was easy to connect the resource application during live sessions	63	2.79	1.52
Interactions using teaching resources was clear and interactive	63	4.67	0.72
Interactions using online teaching resources was understandable	63	4.52	0.62

Table 2 above displays participants' mean reactions to the usefulness of the tools utilized in teaching online classes. Using the services helped participants to achieve the goals of actual schooling. This conveys a fascinating research topic that there should be cooperation and engagement among the students during training. The findings showed that there was organizational alignment, collective learning, and active exchanges between students.

The table showed that the participants were not really clear when they were questioned about the clarity of videos and audio used when doing remote online learning. Unexpectedly, the mean value of 2.67 (1.46) was obtained, indicating that the quality of audio was not good enough for remote online learning. The table indicates that a mean value of 2.79 (1.52) was obtained while attempting to link the tools for online learning.

Interview Questions

As mentioned earlier on 12 participants were randomly selected to participate in the interview which was conducted using the zoom application. The questions were carefully read for them and their opinions were recorded and transcribed. The results are presented below;

Q1. What are your thoughts on the use of technological resources during remote online learning?

The interviewees narrated their thoughts on the use of technological devices during lessons. They indicated that this technological tool's use was new to them and at first complicated to understand and use though they became conversant with them. One of the participants T7 responded *"using these technologies is difficult to understand how they operate and we did not know it before"* Another commented T5; *"It was very difficult to understand what the teacher wanted us to do with the tools but later on it became easy to understand and apply, it helped me"* The students affirmed that the use of these skills resources and tool helped make lesson more fun. They further stated that they were engaged throughout the lessons as they were very busy carrying out the task as if they were in the traditional classroom. In the words of T10, he puts it this way; *"I was troubled when we were asked to register on the Moodle platform for online lessons and I was discouraged, at first it was difficult but later on the lessons were fun as the teacher used lots of games and resourceful materials to ensure that we enjoyed the lessons"* Another participant T1 explained; *"I'm very thankful to my teacher who helped us during this semester by guiding us on how to use the different games and applications like padlet during lessons, I did not feel left out of the class because the teacher always encouraged us to interact with each other, that was lovely"* Another stated; *" I think the whole experience was lovely, I like the breakout sessions where we have to discuss the topic in a particular room of 5, that was great, it seemed as if we were in the classroom, that was so engaging, technology has done a lot for education"* Responses from these participants was an indication that the students were scared of using the technological tools at first though they became conversant with them as the lessons continued. The responses were an indication that students were engaged and motivated during the remote online lessons.

Q2. How motivated were you during lessons?

The responses of the participants were an indication that most of them were motivated during the lesson especially using some of the interactive tools for remote online learning. In the words of T12, he puts it; *"I am greatly motivated to learn especially because I love the way my teacher teaches"* T10 added; *"There is more interaction between teachers and the students, moreover the teacher encourages all of us to use Mentimeter application to interact with each other"* Though most students show their zeal towards learning using online learning, some other students did not enjoy using any of the technological tools or resources. T3 stated; *"I miss the classroom, I miss talking with my teacher and I wish this pandemic will go so we can have lessons normally, I don't enjoy anything"* Another student stated; *"How can I enjoy the class or be motivated when everything is done online, I'm not a fan of this online thing, I want to return to the real classroom"* It was evident that most of the participants were motivated to learn during the online learning though a few complained that they wished to learn was returned to the traditional classroom.

Q3. In what ways did the teacher motivate you during lessons?

The participants indicated that the teacher always engaged them with interactions during each lesson, this encouraged the student to chat with one another during lessons. The participants also indicated that the teacher made use of projects and task to encourage them to learn, they suggested that use of projects and tasks made to them to interact with each other during the lessons to carry out the task collaboratively. They indicated that the use of games during the lessons and at the end of the lesson was so engaging during the lesson as they were immersed in completing the task as assigned by the game—this was very helpful towards engaging the student during the remote online learning. T8 puts it; *"the teacher was very clever in using games to make us love the lessons, he made us play educational games and answer questions with regards to the lesson, it was fun and exciting to*

see your achievement at the end of the games” T4 stated; “the teacher puts on in breakout rooms and encouraged us to use padlets to show our opinions during the discussion, it was fun and he was clever to use these” T3 stated that; “the teacher gave us projects and task to complete then he divided us into groups to complete the task, that was awesome, just as we do in the real classroom” The responses of the student affirm to the strategies used by the teacher to keep the students motivated.

Q4. What technological tools were most effective during the lesson?

The participants thought that zoom break-out rooms, padlets, Mentimeter, nearpod were very effective while learning using online learning platforms. T4, T10, T11 affirmed to this assertion as they thought that these tools were very effective in engaging the students. T10 added; *“I enjoy the use of padlets, nearpod and Mentimeter, also the break out rooms was very interesting to join and it was easy to chat with everyone in the breakout room and contribute to the task assign, technology has done so much to assist education and assist us during this time”* More so, T2, T7, T8, and T12, indicated that the use of projects and task were the most effective tools used during the lesson. they stated that the use of projects and task helped everyone in actively participating throughout the lesson as it was observant that a few students were passive during interactive sessions. In the words of T8, she puts it; *“The use of project was vital in getting everyone to participate during the lesson because some students were not active during the lesson but when the teacher used task and projects, dividing us into groups, all the groups became active as everyone participated”* Their responses are a clear indication that zoom break out rooms, padlets, Mentimeter, nearpods were the most effective tools used during online teaching.

Q5. What were the challenges of using these resources during remote online learning?

The student indicated that the sudden switch from traditional method to online was very stressful, According to T2, T4, T9, they indicated that it was very stressful for students to first register with all the resources and tools to be used for the online lessons from padlet, zoom, to Mentimeter application and this exercise was so stressful for them and they were left on their own to carry out these exercises. The participants indicated that poor internet connection was a strong challenge for most of the students as some of the virtual lessons experience poor video and audio quality which in some cases distorted the lessons, T6 added; *“I remember one of the lessons where you were cut off from the connection and everyone was saying where is the teacher! It was funny for the teacher to lose connection, so the teachers experienced what we were experiencing as well”* T1 stated; *“I joined the lesson late because I live in a small village where internet connection was so poor, what could I do? But I’m glad I joined later on and enjoyed the class sessions”* Another adds; *“first I think the university was selfish to immediately switch from traditional learning to online without informing us and they expected us to comply immediately, there was no orientation rather announcements, that was bad and affected most of us”* It is evident that the sudden switch to online learning, internet connections and stressful nature of the registration process was part of the challenges the students face during the remote online learning.

Discussions

This study provides an array of observations relevant to technology use of the organizations. Survey of LA1’s confirm that technical applications like Zoom, Padlets, Nearpod, Flipgrid, Mentimeter, Boom Cards, vocaroo, were the most widely utilized technological technology. This confirms the conclusion that pads and cards play a valuable function in inspiring students to learn

successfully in online learning climate. According to the finding of this report, student participation is a tactic without the use of technologies.

Philp and Duchesne (2016) had mentioned that students can be engaged even without technology. For project-based learning implemented by the instructor does not result in the best learner experiences among students. Project-based learning was found to be an efficient way of involving students in online learning (Toro-Troconis, Alexander & Frutos-Perez, 2019), and a valuable technique for improving connections among students (Karafil & Oguz, 2019; Paulsen & McCormick, 2020; Maia, Figueiredo, & Serey, 2019), but other researches thought that peer-based learning is more effective (Sridharan & Bond, 2019; Ekblaw, 2016).

Additionally, the research showed that utilizing these tools was successful in meeting the student learning targets, which was a fundamental aspect for student achievement (Redzuan, Lokman, Ali-Othman & Abdullah, 2016; Ritchhart, Church & Morrison, 2011). This concludes that online education was strongly accomplished because it was coordinated and collective (Mavromoustakos, 2017; Sridharan & Bond, 2019). This affirms that instruction is easily understandable by the students as affirmed by research that the usage of tools spawns consistency (Groves, Sellars, Smith & Barber, 2015; Beth, 2020). Video and audio from online learning devices are of poor consistency, and therefore lectures are inconsistent. A big obstacle confronting online learning is internet connectivity issues as hypothesized by T. Mavromoustakos (2017). This study emphasizes that low-speed internet access may be the explanation for inferior audiovisual efficiency. Using services such as learning materials proved beneficial for student interaction.

4. Conclusion

From the study findings, we found that the use of technological tools like zoom, padlets, flipgrid, Mentimeter, and Neapods were very useful in improving the way university students engage in online learning. The study states that other strategies like project-based learning may be incorporated into teaching approaches to encourage inter-participation amongst the students. In the conclusion of the report, it was advised that students should be motivated throughout the epidemic. This paper argued that peer teaching did not improve student interest in learning. Personality analysis work may have an impact on the student's preference for online tools or learning. The study noticed that the online learning process can trigger interference with internet connections, which contributes to poor audio and video quality of the learning materials used for student interaction and online learning.

Based on this finding, school should liaise with telecommunication providers to subsidize the running costs of their communication line such as internet. This might end the problem of lack of a decent internet link faced by the educator and student during the spread of the pandemic.

The drastic transition from in-class approaches to online materials production was inevitable for some of the teaching staff members. Department heads must make sure that instructors will be well-prepared to teach online learning to students. That will assist the instructors to prepare for their lessons by making relevant information readily available for students who require help to prepare for lessons. It will also be the time when the instructor can also instruct the students on the basic requirements of online learning. This would reduce the sensation of uncertainty in the minds of students and convince them that the university would be supportive.

Teachers should understand the attributes of their learners before recommending materials for them. This is useful for online learning as it will help in selecting resources and online tools that will both assist the teacher and the students in the online learning process. These reforms would have a favorable impact on learning and growth of students.

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References

- Beth, H (March 2, 2020) Using Mentimeter in and out of the classroom. *Learning Innovation Unit*. Retrieved from; <https://fetliu.net/blog/using-mentimeter-in-and-out-of-the-classroom/>
- Beltrán-Martín, I. (2019). *Using Padlet for collaborative learning*. 1-8. 10.4995/HEAD19.2019.9188.
- CNA (2020, March 6) Cyprus shuts schools, locks down hospitals over coronavirus
Retrieved from: <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/news/world/cyprus-shutters-schools-locks-down-hospitals-over-coronavirus-12524022>
- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks. Sage Publications, Inc.^[LSEP]
- Daily Sabah (2020, March 14) Cyprus, north, and south, shuts borders to prevent the spread of coronavirus. Retrieved from <https://www.dailysabah.com/world/europe/cyprus-north-and-south-shuts-borders-to-prevent-spread-of-coronavirus>
- Demosthenous, G, Panaoura, R. & Eteokleous, N. (2020). The Use of Collaborative Assignment in Online Learning Environments: The Case of Higher Education. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science*. 4. 108-117. 10.46328/ijtes.v4i2.43.
- Ekblaw, R. (2016). Effective use of group projects in online learning. *Contemporary issues in education research – Third Quarter*, 9 (3), 121-128.
- Fuchs, B. (2014). The writing is on the wall: using Padlet for whole-class engagement. *LOEX Quarterly*, 40(4), 7-9.
- Groves, M., Sellars, C., Smith, J., and Barber, A. (2015). Factors affecting student engagement: A case study examining two cohorts of students attending a post-1992 university in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 4(2), 27-37.
- Hale, E, and Ali, E (2019) Current Problems in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus Education System, *Sakarya university journal of education*, 9(2), 282-303. doi: 10.19126/suje.516474
- Ironsi, S.C (2017) *Effect of test anxiety on academic performance of EFL Learners*. Lambert Academic Publishing, ISBN:978-620-2-070620-3
- Karafil, B and Oğuz, A. (2019). Examining Factors Affecting Student Engagement in English Preparatory Classes According to Student Opinions. *Üniversitepark Bülten*. 8. 117-133. 10.22521/unibulletin.2019.82.2.
- Kleinsmith, C. L. (2017). *The effects of using Padlet on the academic performance and engagement of students in a fifth-grade basic skills mathematics classroom*, Rowan University. RowanDigitalWorks.

-
- Maia, M, Figueiredo, J, and Serey, D. (2019). *Online Student Engagement: A Case Study in Teaching of Programming*. 51. 10.5753/cbie.sbie.2019.51.
- Mavromoustakos, S. (2017). *Student Engagement Practices for Computer Science Students in Online Learning Environments*.
- Muhammed, I.A (2020) North Cyprus confirms 6th coronavirus. Anadolu Agency. Retrieved from: <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/latest-on-coronavirus-outbreak/northern-cyprus-confirms-6th-coronavirus-case/1766813>
- Near East University (2020, March 14) Announcement for live lessons; Google Hangout Meet! Retrieved from <https://www.uzem.neu.edu.tr>
- Odo C.R. and Eze, C. U (2017) Effect of Flipped Learning on Students Achievement in Computer Science in Tertiary Institution in Enugu State. *London Journal of Research in Computer Science and Technology*, Vol 1, 45-50
- Paulsen, J., and McCormick, A. (2020). Reassessing Disparities in Online Learner Student Engagement in Higher Education. *Educational Researcher*. 49. 0013189X1989869.10.3102/0013189X19898690.
- Philp, J., and Duchesne, S. (2016). Exploring engagement in tasks in the language classroom. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 36, 50-72.
- Ragusa, A. T., and Crampton, A. (2018). Sense of connection, identity, and academic success in distance education: Sociologically exploring online learning environments. *Rural Society*, 27(2): 125-142, pp.15.
- Redzuan, F., Lokman, A. M., Ali Othman, Z., and Abdullah, S. (2016). Kansei Design Model for Engagement in Online Learning: *A Proposed Model*. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Informatics Engineering and Information Science*, 64-78.
- Ritchhart, R., Church, M., and Morrison, K. (2011) *Making thinking visible: How to promote engagement, understanding, and independence for all learners*, San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Shola G. O, Selira, K., and Mustafa, I (2011) Online Education in North Cyprus Universities: Case Study Eastern Mediterranean University. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 28 (2011) 536 – 541
- Sridharan, B. and Boud, D. (2019) *The effects of peer judgments on teamwork and self-assessment ability in collaborative group work*. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*. DOI: 10.1080/02602938.2018.1545898.
- Stone, C (2019) 'Online learning in Australian higher education: Opportunities, challenges, and transformations', *Student Success* 10(2): 1-11, p.2.
- The University of Kyrenia. (March 12, 2020) An important announcement by the university.
-

Retrieved from: <https://kyrenia.edu.tr/important-announcement-by-university-of-kyrenia-rectorate-for-our-students/?lang=en>

Toro-Troconis, M, Alexander, J., and Frutos-Perez, M. (2019). Assessing Student Engagement in Online Programmes: Using Learning Design and Learning Analytics. *International Journal of Higher Education*. 8. 171. 10.5430/ijhe.v8n6p171.

Tugun, V, Uzunboylu, H, and Ozdamli, F. (2017). Coding Education in a Flipped Classroom. *Technology Education Management Informatics*. 6. 599-606. 10.18421/TEM63-23.

Yakın Doğu Üniversitesi (March 30, 2020) Announcement! Alternative fora live lessons: Google Hangout Meet. Retrieved from: <https://uzem.neu.edu.tr/>

Yildirim, A. and Simsek, H. (2011). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri*. Ankara: Seckin Yayıncılık